

NEGATIVE FACTORS OF THE TECHNOSPHERE ON THE
HUMAN BODY EFFECTS AND PROTECTION FROM THEM

Tanirbergenov Baxtiyar Abdijamilovich

Inspector of the Emergency Management Training

Center of the Republic of Karakalpakstan

tanirbergenovbaxtiyar23@gcom

Key words: technosphere, harmful substances, negative factors, chemical factors, physical factors, air, water, soil, food, bacteria.

Dangerous and harmful substances that manifest themselves in the technosphere in the history of the rule and have a negative effect on biological objects are negative factors of the technosphere.

First of all, the negative factors of the technosphere are those that disrupt the normal state of a person, harm his health and the environment. Currently, there are more than 100 types of negative factors. Negative factors affecting people are divided into two types: natural (natural) and anthropogenic [1].

According to the nature of the movement, they are divided into:

-chemical factors: air, water, dust, food, as well as various chemicals that make up pollutants (waste and waste from enterprises);

- physical factors: increase in the amount of dust and gas in the air; increase the level of noise and vibration; electromagnetic fields and radiation; insufficient lighting, ultraviolet and infrared radiation, sharp and falling objects, etc.

- biological factors: contamination of air, water, soil, food with pathogenic bacteria and their metabolic products;

- psychophysiological factors: physical and neuropsychic overloads (mental overload, analyzer overload, work monotony and emotional overloads).

Chemical and physical factors of the technosphere include a number of factors in their negative effects.

Chemical factors of the technosphere: Harmful - a substance that can cause injuries, diseases or deviations in health when it comes into contact with the human body. Harmful substances include: vapors, gases, liquids, aerosols, chemical compounds, mixtures, etc [2].

Chemical harmful substances are divided into the following depending on their practical application.

- industrial poisons used in production;
- pesticides used in agriculture;
- chemical drugs and medicinal preparations;
- household chemicals used in the form of food additives (vinegar);
- sanitary, personal hygiene and cosmetic products;
- plant composition and biologically toxic substances from animals;
- toxic substances (OS).

According to the nature of the effect, chemically dangerous and harmful factors are divided into:

- nervous - paralytic - causes convulsions and paralysis (nicotine, pesticides, agents);
- skin-resorptive - causes local inflammation in combination with general toxic effects (vinegar essence, dichloroethane, arsenic);
- general toxic - leads to poisoning of the whole organism or damage to its separate systems: central nervous system, hematopoietic system, kidney liver (alcohol and its surrogates, carbon monoxide);
- suffocating - toxic brain swelling (nitric oxide, some agents);
- tearing and irritating - causes irritation of the mucous membranes of the eyes, nose, throat, lungs, skin (pairs of strong acids and alkalis);

- psychotropic - causes disruption of mental activity and consciousness (drugs, atropine);
- sensitization - formaldehyde acting as an allergen, solvents, varnishes;
- mutagen - causes a violation of the genetic code, changes in genetic information (lead, manganese, radioactive isotopes);
- carcinogen - causes malignant tumors (chromium, nickel, asbestos);
- affecting reproductive (childbearing) function (mercury, lead, styrene, radioactive isotopes) [3].

The last three types of exposure to harmful substances - mutagenic, carcinogenic and effects on reproductive function - are called long-term effects of chemical compounds on the body. This is a specific action that manifests itself not during the period of exposure, but over long periods, years and even decades.

According to selective toxicity, poisons are divided into:

- heart, has a cardiotoxic effect (medicines, plant poisons, metal salts);
- causing nervous and mental disorders (alcohol, drugs, carbon monoxide, some pesticides, sleeping pills);
- liver (chlorinated hydrocarbons, poisonous mushrooms, phenols and aldehydes);
- kidney (heavy metals, ethylene glycol, oxalic acid);
- blood (aniline, nitrites, arsenic hydrogen);
- lungs (nitrogen oxide, ozone, phosgene).

The human body is able to neutralize the effects of poisons in different ways. The first and main one is the change in the chemical structure of the poison in the human body as a result of metabolism. Organic compounds undergo processes of oxidation, reduction, and division, resulting in the formation of less harmful and less active substances in the body [2].

The second method of detoxification is the removal of poison through breathing, digestion, kidneys, sweat and sebaceous glands, skin. Heavy metals, as a

rule, are excreted through the gastrointestinal tract, some organic compounds - unchanged - through the lungs, and after partial physicochemical changes, through the kidneys.

The entire set of physical negative factors of the technosphere can be divided into the following groups of parameters according to the nature of their impact:

- power factors - related to the effect of acoustic, vibration, shock and other power parameters on human and environmental objects.

- electromagnetic factors - covers the entire spectrum of electric and magnetic phenomena, including high voltage, ultra-high frequency and laser effects, as well as other types of electromagnetic radiation.

- ionizing (radiation) factors - related to the radioactivity of a very large group of chemical elements and isotopes used by humans in various fields.

Among the main negative power factors of the technosphere are acoustic parameters, including audible noise in all its forms. Mechanical vibrations in elastic bodies cause the propagation of elastic waves, which are called acoustic vibrations. Acoustic (sound) vibrations propagating in space create an acoustic field. The distance between the two nearest particles of the medium oscillating in the same phase is called the wavelength. The speed of propagation of a wave depends on the density of the medium in which it propagates, the distance from the source of the wave, and other factors.

USED LITERATURES

1. Безопасность жизнедеятельности: учебник / под ред. Полиевский С.А..
- М.: Academia, 2018. - 96 с.
2. Полиевский, С.А. Безопасность жизнедеятельности: Учебник / С.А. Полиевский. - М.: Академия, 2018. - 416 с.
3. Исмоилов А. Т., Усмонов Қ.Т. Ҳаёт фаолияти хавфсизлиги. Ижтимоий-гуманитар факультет талабалари учун ўқув қўлланма.- СамДЧТИ. 2009 й. 120 бет.

